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Book Reviews

Fuchs, Ottmar. *Committed Spirituality*. Stuttgart, Germany: Kohlhammer. *Praktische Theologie heute*, Band 168. 2020. ISBN 978-3-17-037549-9. pp. 374. € 29/-.

The Christian faith can lead to a spirituality that provides the power and energy needed to act justly. Human solidarity, on the other hand, has the potential to open us up to the Christian faith's contents. Christian hope, in particular, invites us to participate in a universal solidarity that does not exclude others and never serves solely one's own interests without regard for others. Ottmar Fuchs, Professor emeritus of Practical Theology, University of Tübingen, Germany, has pointed out this relationship throughout his entire practical theology in numerous writings, and now delivers key outcomes of his work in an English-language collection.

The churches are at the service of this universal commitment. The author advocates the stance of a faith that embraces all people into God's love and an ethics that is not bound by any frontiers in the heated debates between identity-rootedness-fundamentalism and openness-universalism-solidarity formations. It is a vote for a church that is more self-giving than victorious at the expense of others, and that profiles all of its instruments in this manner, from the church's social and

ceremonial organization to its various exterior contacts. It's about a faith and a church format that doesn't let the respective exclusivistic sections of churches and society off the hook for caring.

The writing emerges from different periods of the author's teaching and research at the universities of Bamberg and Tübingen. They represent the result of his pastoral theological and practical theological work and what he considers very significant for contemporary times.

The major theme of this book is the connection between faith and commitment, between spirituality and social practice, following the Second Vatican Council (p. 13).

The book first reflects on the "Realisations of the Good News." Then the author reflects on "The Contexts and Challenges." This is followed by "The Hermeneutical Keys of Memory." This is followed by a reflection on "Towards a New Mission." Then the author takes up the issue of "The Responsibility in Church Offices." The final sections dwell "Spiritual Traces" ("Priest Mothers" and "God Mothers") on "Translations" on poetry, sermons and meditations. The book also contains an appendix of Publications and translation references.

For the author, it is clear here that the biblical personality of God maintains a level of secret. In spite of the many unique stories of encountering God in the Bible, God generally is not definable (p. 20). Still, the call of the community of believers is to serve humanity. So he quotes Pope John XXIII, "We are oriented more than ever today, certainly more than in the last centuries, to serve humankind as such and not really the Catholics and are oriented in the first instance and above all to defend the rights of humankind and not only those of the Catholic Church" (p. 23).

In the context of assertion of religious identity and growing fundamentalism, the author is emphatic. "I do not want to diminish religious faith. Instead, my aim is to deepen the Christian or Islamic faith in which religion takes place, to the

heart of each belief. Now to an average core, or to give God the greatness and magnanimity, God is himself and she's to be praised for inexhaustible mercy, for I'm sure that this deepening of our faith will bring especially the Christian faith to its own core and heart of identity. Tolerance will overcome difficulties only if it is rooted in a certain realization of the Christian faith itself. I believe every religion has its own possibilities and resources for similar transformation and to take responsibility to avoid fundamentalism in one's own complex identity" (p. 72).

The book also contains creative reflections on violence in Biblical texts, Biblical lamentations. Church's mission in a pluralistic world and Eschatology. In our world where so much is written on spirituality, some of which are questionable and hazy, here is one book that emphasises on the liberative and humanising potential of Christian spirituality, with its emphasis on inclusivity, solidarity and caring for the marginalised. This is a book highly recommended for those interested in spirituality, Christian faith and social involvement. As the title affirms genuine spirituality stems from deep commitment.

Pandikattu, Kuruvilla SJ (ed.) *Encountering, Experiencing and Enabling: Towards a World-Church, Inspired by Prof Lothar Lies, SJ*. New Delhi: ISPCK. 2021. ISBN: 9789390569793 pp. 432+ xxxiv \$22/-.

“It is neither a culture of confrontation nor a culture of conflict which builds harmony within and between peoples, but rather a culture of **encounter** and a culture of dialogue; this is the only way to peace” (Pope Francis at the audience, Sep 1, 2013). How do we visualize the Church of the future? How can the Church become more vitalized and vibrant? How will the world Church of the future look like? These

are some of the questions posed in this book on the world Church, a theme very close to **Prof Lothar Lies, SJ**, University of Innsbruck, Austria.

Experiencing the Other

The answer the authors of the book believe has to do with genuine encounter and authentic experience with truly enables us. The encounter of the other as other with diverse religious, ethnic, political sociological and other identities is the stepping stone to encounter the Wholly Other, God. Such an encounter of people and God help us experience the breadth and depth of human relationship leading to an all-inclusive and enriching experience of God. This encounter-experience enables us as individuals and community to embrace the other/s who are constitutive of ourselves. The Church of the future could be visualised thus as one that encounters the world intimately, experiences the other warmly and in the process enables each other. That is a vision close to Pope Francis too.

This volume is a volume written by scholars who have close ties with the University of Innsbruck and Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology, India. It also attempts to remember Fr Lothar Lies and pay homage to the incredible contribution he has accomplished for the universal and local Churches in India and Austria. This volume explores Christian living as expiring and encounter the person of Christ and our fellow human beings as well as the whole of nature. The emphasis on the encounter (*Begegnung*) with the others and the “Wholly Other” (“*ganz Andere.*”), it is hoped, will unfold deeper dimensions of our Christian spirituality.

Such an encounter is enabling and presupposed collaboration, networking, acceptance and understanding. The writers of this volume, inspired by Prof Lothar Lies, believes that such an ongoing dialogue, based on genuine encounter and mutually enriching experiences among religious traditions is the need of the hour for the Church and the world.

The Themes of the Book

The first part of the book looks at encountering the other as experiencing the other and oneself. So, the first article in this section by **Dr Paul Raj Mariapushpam**, Jnana Deepa, Pune, explores Paul's encounter with Christ and the Damascus experience and looks at its significance for contemporary men and women. This is followed by the article of **Dr Alangaram Arockiam, SJ**, Loyola College, Chennai, that explores the encounter between God and human beings through the category of covenant and looks at the Eucharist as a covenant experience. **Rev Joseph Cardozo, SJ**, Jnana Deepa, Pune, studies encountering and experiencing from the perspective of Christ's standards, according to St. Ignatius of Loyola.

This is followed by **Dr Richard Lopes, SJ**, Jnana Deepa, Pune, who visualized the Church of the future and an enabling Church. The next article by Dr Herman Tirkey, Jnana Deepa, Pune, situates the encounter of the Gospel in the multicultural context of India.

The second section deals with the Church's mission in the pluri-cultural context of both India and Europe. **Dr Boris Repschinski, SJ**, Leopold-Franzens-Universität Innsbruck, introduces this section by understanding pluralism as the foundational principle of the New Testament. **Dr Andreas Vonach**, also of Leopold-Franzens-Universität Innsbruck, studies the four existential questions connected to pluralism from Christian perspectives. In this context of plurality, **Dr Joseph Lobo, SJ**, St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Bengaluru, looks at the theological foundations of cross-credal encounters. This is followed by **Dr Thomas Karimundackal SJ**, who takes up the encounter between Jesus and the Samaritan woman as an illustration of cross-cultural encounter.

Such an encounter also enables and empowers all the partners involved. So the third section deals with the prophetic and

liberative aspects of genuine encounter. **Dr VM Jose, SJ**, Jnana Deepa, Pune, looks on the mission of the Indian Church towards the tribal community providing them with dignity and liberation. **Dr Jose Thayil, SJ**, explores the ecological concerns of today and relates them to our deep experience of nature. **Rev Clement Jesudoss Santhanam, SJ**, studies the practical and epistemic authority as encountering. The next article by Dr Leonard Fernando, St. Joseph's College, Tiruchirappalli, deals with the person of Origen as a man of encounter and his significance for today. In the final article in this section **Prof Pudota Rayappa John, Vidyajyoti** College of Theology, New Delhi, looks at the sacraments as means of encountering Christ and fellow human beings.

The final section deal with the need for dialogue for the world church and reflects on dialogue as a way of life for the Church. **Dr Chacko Nadakkeveliyil**, Thrissur, looks at the world as a gratuitous gift of God and explores the universe as the ultimate free lunch, based on Stephen Hawking. Clement Valluvassery, Pontifical Institute of Theology and Philosophy, Alwaye, then focuses on the need for dialogue for a meaningful and harmonious future both for the world and the church. **Dr Kuruvilla Pandikattu, SJ**, Jnana Deepa, draws inspiration from Bede Griffiths, who fostered active dialogue between Christianity and Hinduism. **Rev Anthony Raj**, Papal Seminary, Pune, investigates experiencing as understanding, inspired by his encounter with Dr Lothar Lies and by the Ignatian spirituality. Finally, Rev Seraphim Stanley Tirkey pleads for an authentic dialogue between Church and cultures going beyond relativism and ethnocentrism. Such an approach will enable the Church to dialogue with other wisdom traditions in a spirit of mutual respect and dignity.

Travelling a Common Path

This volume is the product of the ongoing dialogue and collaboration between the Theology Faculty of Innsbruck and Jnana Deepa Pune. The aim of this volume, inspired by Prof

Lothar Lies, who was a bridge-builder between these two centres of theological learning, is to propose ways and means of building a genuine world church, where the strengths of individual churches are acknowledged, the differences are respected and a common path is travelled to reach the goal of genuine and joyful Christian living.

The book is enriched by messages from **Rev Bernhard Bürgler SJ**, Provinzial der Zentraleuropäischen Provinz der Jesuiten; Germany, **Rev Jerome Stanislaus D'Souza SJ**, Vice-Chancellor, Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology; India, **P. Dr. Christian Marte, SJ**, Rector, Jesuitenkolleg, Innsbruck, Austria, **Prof. Dr Francis Gonsalves, SJ**, President, Jnana Deepa, Pune, **Rev Bhausaheb Sansare SJ**, Rector, Papal Seminary, Pune and **Rev Dr Andreas Scherman SJ**, Rektor, Collegium Canisianum, Innsbruck, Austria.

The book is a remarkable contribution towards a world Church that is vibrant, alive and based on experience and encounter! Based on the Christian experience of the Good News it attempts to enable humanity to live committed and compassionate lives.

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